

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

Report on the Clustering Event Nr. 1

Deliverable 9.5

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1. Abstract

The Clustering Event was organized in collaboration between [TipESM](#) and [ClimTip](#), two sister projects funded under the same Horizon Europe call on Climate-related tipping points, on 7-10 April 2025. The event took place in Paris, France, hosted at the Henri Poincaré Institute of the Sorbonne University and online. It consisted of three parts: (1) a scientific conference, (2) a cross-project workshop (breakout sessions), and (3) a session on storylines.

The scientific conference was arranged around five themes related to tipping points research:

- Cryosphere;
- Biosphere, including the Amazon;
- Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), Subpolar Gyre (SPG), and uncertainties of their projections;
- Tipping points prediction methodologies;
- Impacts and communication of tipping points research results.

Each theme featured scientific talks from several projects, along with ample time for discussion of scientific results. The discussions continued in the breakout groups during the cross-project workshop, which was organised across the same five themes. To round off, the event featured a hands-on session, where participants practised developing storylines for selected tipping events. The Book of Abstracts of this Event is available in Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/15302644>

2. The Cluster

2.1 Objectives of the Clustering Event

The event brought together scientists working across several projects and initiatives on different aspects of climate tipping points (TPs), e.g., from precursors to impacts, and with various methodologies, e.g., from Earth System Models, mathematical modelling, observational data, to paleodata. The aim was to facilitate knowledge exchange between them and better understand each other's approaches to studying TPs, and identify areas for potential collaboration across projects.

Photo 1: Clustering Event participants outside the venue, the Henri Poincaré Institute at Sorbonne University in Paris, France.

2.2 Represented Projects and Initiatives

The Clustering Event gathered representatives of various international projects, Earth System Modelling groups, and TPs initiatives. A total of 124 participants attended the event, with over 90 present in Paris. Including TipESM and ClimTip, a total of 32 various projects and initiatives were represented, funded by the European Union, Advanced Research and Invention Agency (ARIA), European Space Agency (ESA), UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), and other national funding agencies.

The projects and organizations represented **via the external collaborators and the advisors to the TipESM:**

- **NCAR (USA).** NCAR is key for its contribution to the development of the ESM protocol TipESM_core, and the possible realisation of experiments with CESM.
- **JAMSTEC (Japan).** JAMSTEC's contribution is key to the development of the ESM protocol TipESM_core, and the possible realisation of experiments with MIROC-ESM. JAMSTEC also shares analysis methods and results with TipESM.

- **CNR-ISAC (Italy).** CNR-ISAC contribution is key to the development of a catalogue of TPs in the climate system, analysis of reversibility of TPs and rare extreme events in trigger TPs, as well as the synthesis results for risk registers.
- **WCRP/FutureEarth project TIPMIP for its key role in developing** the TIPMIP protocols.
- **WCRP “Grand Challenge on Extremes” and lighthouse activity “Safe Landing Space”** for the key link to the WCRP initiatives on tipping points.
- **Carbon Brief Ltd.**, with a contribution to dissemination and communication, but also to the work on storylines.

The ESA-funded projects represented at the Event were:

- **CryoTipping:** working on cryosphere tipping led by Northumbria University, UK (looking at Thwaites glacier in West Antarctica, and bringing together observational datasets for detection of signs of Marine Ice Sheet Instability and comparing these to numerical simulations of grounding line evolution in the past).
- **RESETLakes:** combining Earth observation with model-based analyses to investigate lakes as tipping elements in their catchment area. Led by Eawag, Switzerland.
- **PREDICT:** Predicting Resilience and Early Detection of Impending Climate Transitions. Exploring use of multiple lines of evidence and data fusion techniques for biosphere tipping elements, to enhance the detection and interpretation of early warning signals & assess risk, led by the University of Exeter, UK.
- **SIRENE:** Satellite Information for Resilience Monitoring & Early Warning of Ecosystem Tipping Points. To assess and benchmark vegetation data for resilience metrics and develop improved metrics with fully propagated uncertainty, on a global scale. Led by the Technical University Munich, Germany.
- **TIME:** Abrupt changes in marine ecosystems, investigating ecosystem resilience in 8 case studies, early warning signals, led by Plymouth Marine Laboratory, UK.
- **TIPSOO:** project related to ocean circulation focused on southern ocean overturning, and its response to freshwater flux increase, led by Albavator in Spain.

Projects and climate models represented through the Clustering Event participants:

Project name	Funding	Led by	Key focus area
AdvanTip	UK Advanced Research and Invention Agency	Univ. Exeter	Early warning indicators and role of the Subpolar Gyre
CDRTerra	German Federal Ministry of Education and Research	Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich (LMU)	Research Project on Carbon Dioxide Removal
ClimTip	Horizon Europe (Horizon EU)	Technical University of Munich (TUM)	Quantifying tipping points and their impacts
Critical Earth	Horizon 2020	University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	Mathematical methods for assessing mechanisms and risks of tipping points
CSSP Brazil	Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS) via Met Office	Met Office	Climate Science for Services Partnerships Brazil - development of climate services
EC-Earth	Several sources of funding	EC-Earth brings together 30 research institutes from 12 European countries	Development of the Earth System Model
EPOC	Horizon EU	Univ. Hamburg	Observational and model experiments on AMOC
ESiWACE3	Horizon EU, EuroHPC and national funding	Barcelona Supercomputing Centre	Development of high-resolution weather and climate models
ESM2025	Horizon 2020	Météo France-CNRM	Building the new generation Earth System Models
FORCLIMA	ERC Consolidator Grants	Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Forecasting climate surprises on longer timescales

ISIMIP	Different sources of funding	The ISIMP management group is hosted by the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project
MadGod	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	University of Copenhagen	Machine Learning for Earth System Modelling
NextGEMS	Horizon 2020	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology	Building the new generation ESMs
ObsSea4Clim	Horizon EU	Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)	Ocean observations in support of climate assessments and models
OCEAN ICE	Horizon EU, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	DMI	Impacts of Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on climate
OceanICU	Horizon EU	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	Role of the ocean in the global carbon cycle
OptimESM	Horizon EU	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)	Building the new generation of ESMs
Past to Future	Horizon EU	Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Research Utrecht (IMAU)	Improving ESMs using paleodata
PROMOTE	ARIA	National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)	Early warning system for SPG and GIS
RESCUE	Horizon EU	Barcelona Supercomputing Centre	Updating climate projection scenarios, including carbon dioxide removal portfolios
SORTED	ARIA	UK's National Oceanography Centre (NOC)	Early warning indication of Subpolar Gyre collapse
TeMPlex	Agence Nationale de la	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)	Changes in the climate system or any of its components in terms

	Recherche (ANR)		of a change in its topological structure
TerraFIRMA	UKRI	Met Office	Impacts, risks and mitigation action
TIPMIP	Different sources of funding	PIK hosts the initiative	Tipping Point Modelling Intercomparison Project
TRACCS	France 2030	CNRS and Météo-France	Transforming climate modelling for climate services
WorldTrans	Horizon EU	Norwegian Meteorological Institute	Integrated assessment models

3. Report on the sessions

3.1 Scientific conference

The TipESM-ClimTip scientific conference took place on 7-8 April 2025 and covered five science themes related to tipping points research:

- Cryosphere
- Biosphere incl. Amazon
- AMOC, SPG, and uncertainties of their projections
- Tipping points prediction methodologies
- Impacts and communication of tipping points research results

Photo 2: Conference participants engaging in a Q&A session.

The full conference programme can be found in Appendix 1. The presentation abstracts can be found in the Book of Abstracts, published on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/15302644>.

The contents of each session, along with the list of available presentations, are provided below in the document.

3.1.1 Science theme 1: Cryosphere

The ice sheets of Greenland and Antarctica are widely recognised as major tipping elements of the Earth System, with the potential for global impact through millennial-scale commitments to sea level rise. Additionally, ice mass loss can impact global ocean circulation, potentially triggering the tipping of other elements. This session addressed how the response of these ice sheets to climate change is currently being modelled, and how to deal with the considerable uncertainty in their past history, relevant physical mechanisms and likelihood of future abrupt and irreversible change.

Presentations:

- “The reversibility of ice sheet and sea level responses at different global warming levels in a state-of-the-art Earth System Model”. Presentation by: Robin Smith, University of Reading.
- “Antarctica’s inner values – tapping Antarctica’s sub-surface to project its future evolution”. Presentation by: Johannes Sutter, University of Bern.
- “The fates of the Greenland ice sheet under the idealised scenarios of the TIPMIP-ESM protocol as simulated by EC-Earth3-ESM”. Presentation by: Jorge Bernales, Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI).
- The Antarctic response to a 1% Annual Increase in Atmospheric CO₂. Presentation by: Javier Blasco, Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research. <https://zenodo.org/records/15301712>

3.1.2 Science Theme 2: Biosphere, including Amazon

This session encompassed a variety of aspects related to tipping points in the Biosphere. The main points of discussion covered the response of various ecosystems to external forcings, how these affect their resilience, and the potential impacts of resilience loss on these ecosystems and society. These debates

contributed to assessing the likelihood and risks of approaching or crossing eventual tipping points in the Biosphere.

Presentations:

- “Amazon forest decline driven by both climate change and land-use change”. Presentation by: Julia Pongratz, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich (LMU).
- “Bridging Data and Theory for Monitoring Resilience Changes in Tropical Forests”. Presentation by: Lana Blaschke, Technical University of Munich (TUM). <https://zenodo.org/records/15229173>
- “Disaster-induced displacement as a potential social tipping element”. Presentation by: Sandra Zimmermann, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK).
- “Deep sea and seafloor ecosystem response to net-zero and negative emissions”. Presentation by: Friederike Fröb, University of Bergen.

3.1.3 Science theme 3: AMOC, SPG, and uncertainties of their projections

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) plays a crucial role in transporting heat and freshwater throughout the climate system. It is known to be sensitive to increasing greenhouse gases, and climate models show that it has the potential for abrupt tipping behaviour under some circumstances. On a more regional scale, the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre (SPG) circulation plays an essential role in the AMOC and can exhibit more localised tipping. This session addressed the potential future evolution of the AMOC and SPG. A particular theme was related to exploring how limited (and sometimes biased) information from models can be combined with limited available observations to improve predictions of future behaviour, including early warning of tipping.

Presentations:

- “On-going and future changes of the AMOC: what can we learn from combining models and various sources of observations?”. Presentation by: Didier Swingedouw, University of Bordeaux.
- “AMOC thresholds in CMIP6 models: NAHosMIP”. Presentation by: Laura Jackson, Met Office. <https://zenodo.org/records/15229199>
- “Reconciled warning signals in observations and models imply approaching AMOC tipping point”. Presentation by: Yechul Shin, Seoul National University (SNU).

- “Statistically Optimal Fingerprints for the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation and the Sub-Polar Gyre”. Presentation by: Bahar Emirzade, Technical University of Munich (TUM). <https://zenodo.org/records/15229217>
- “Critical Salinity as an Early Warning of Tipping Point in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre”. Presentation by: Lucas Almeida, University of Bordeaux. <https://zenodo.org/records/15229243>
- “Collapse of the AMOC in a Strongly Eddying Ocean-Only Model”. Presentation by: Henk Dijkstra, University of Utrecht. <https://zenodo.org/records/15266943>
- “Noise-shaped hysteresis cycles of the AMOC under increasing CO2 forcing”. Presentation by: Susanna Corti, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR). <https://zenodo.org/records/15261568>

3.1.4 Science theme 4: Tipping points prediction methodology

We have seen numerous studies exploring the concept of “early warnings,” i.e., monitoring the resilience of tipping elements over the observed (or reconstructed) time period. The session focused on limitations, uncertainties, and potential solutions related to these methods, as well as methods for detecting tipping events in time series and estimating the time (or parameter value) when tipping might occur in the future.

Presentations:

- “Assessment paper on high-impact climate events, tipping points and irreversible regional impacts”. Presentation by: Gabi Hegerl, University of Edinburgh. <https://zenodo.org/records/15274055>
- “Uncertainties in Tipping Warning and Prediction”. Presentation by: Maya Ben-Yami, Technical University of Munich (TUM). <https://zenodo.org/records/15229274>
- “Comparing Resilience Concepts in Bifurcating Systems of Intermediate Complexity”. Presentation by: Andreas Morr, Technical University of Munich (TUM).
- “Cataloguing abrupt shifts in CMIP6 models: from ocean physics to biogeochemistry”. Presentation by: Eike Köhn, Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL).

3.1.5 Science theme 5: Impacts and communication of tipping points research results

This session explored emerging scientific, societal, and financial perspectives on tipping points. It featured a keynote from Robert Vautard, offering a timely update on the IPCC’s upcoming 7th Assessment Report and the scientific hurdles ahead for Working Group I. Following this, the session unpacked how tipping points are communicated across sectors—from the dynamics of scientific consensus and public engagement to the

practical framing of risks in the financial world, and the early findings from ongoing research into societal and ecosystem impacts. Together, these talks contributed to crucial debates on how we define, assess, and communicate tipping point risks across different audiences and disciplines.

Presentations:

- “The IPCC Outlines of AR7 and challenges for WGI”. Presentation by: Robert Vautard, Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL); Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). <https://zenodo.org/records/15266997>
- “Tipping Points in Climate Communication: Scientific Consensus, Risk Perception, and Public Engagement”. Presentation by: Imke Hoppe, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich (LMU).
- “From Data to Dollars: Making Tipping Points Tangible”. Presentation by: Russ Bowdrey, MSCI.
- “Societal and ecosystem impacts of climate tipping points. First results from TipESM”. Presentation by: Andrew Hartley, Met Office. <https://zenodo.org/records/15229293>.

3.2 Breakout sessions

Following the scientific conference, the discussions continued in breakout sessions during a cross-project workshop.

Photo 3: Clustering Event participants continuing discussions in the break room.

3.2.1 Cryosphere breakout session

The session explored whether participants in TipESM, ClimTip, and related projects like TIPMIP and ISMIP are aware of the work being conducted across the different groups and identified potential areas for coordination. It was discussed that a shared understanding or agreed-upon definition of "tipping"—such as the one proposed in the TIPMIP paper (see the TipESM deliverable D1.1)—could help align efforts across these initiatives. Additionally, it may be worth assessing whether aspects of model initialisation or spin-up procedures can be transferred between Earth System Models and Ice Sheet Models, or whether each application requires its unique setup. Lastly, the participants discussed potential contributions from ClimTip domain experts in TipESM's work on the Risk Register and Register of Early Warning Indicators.

3.2.2 Biosphere incl. Amazon breakout session

Several key questions emerged for this session regarding the investigation of tipping points in tropical rainforests. One topic of interest was the potential added value of convection-resolving models in capturing critical dynamics in regions such as the Amazon. Participants also set out to discuss the need for a coordinated effort to differentiate between variables that are early warning indicators and those that

change in response to crossing a tipping point. Another key point for discussion was how to interpret and reconcile partially contradictory results across different Earth System Models. Finally, the session proposed a discussion on whether insights gained from Amazon-focused tipping point studies could be meaningfully transferred to other tropical systems, such as the Congo rainforest, or whether distinct regional dynamics would require separate treatment.

3.2.3 AMOC, SPG and uncertainties of their projections breakout session

This session discussed the nature of abrupt changes in the SPG and their distinction from changes in the AMOC. It was explained that both SPG and AMOC abrupt changes are associated with changes in deep convection; however, shifts in deep convection may induce SPG abrupt changes without affecting AMOC. At the session, the group also discussed wind-driven, buoyancy-driven, and overflow components of the SPG, considering whether each should be analysed separately and how their importance might vary with timescale. The discussion during this session centred on whether to focus on outcomes or impacts, with the shared goal of providing early warnings. A key point raised in the discussion was around the availability of data to construct machine-learning-based warning systems for an SPG collapse. Participants also discussed the potential use of pre-industrial control runs, where regular abrupt events can be observed across several models, and whether models of intermediate complexity could be useful. The session considered agreeing upon a small set of variables and types of events to monitor, with salinity being questioned due to its unreliability, but with sea level being suggested as a potential focus. Furthermore, links across the tasks in both projects were discussed as well as how to collaborate going forward. Outputs regarding collaboration opportunities included a decision on a dedicated group meeting similar to a previous SPG abrupt changes meeting held in February 2025.

3.2.4 Tipping points prediction methodology breakout session

This session focused on methods for detecting tipping points and how these different approaches can be complementary across the projects. A number of different abrupt shift detection tools have been developed, and/or are in development in TipESM, ClimTip and TIPMIP. This discussion aimed to consider a common benchmarking exercise, and/or a common catalogue of shifts in CMIP data.

3.2.5. Impacts and communication of tipping points research results breakout session

This session explored the vital role of stakeholders in the success of our projects. The discussion began by revisiting the lists of stakeholders already mapped out in the projects, ranging from scientific communities

and climate services to policymakers and the general public. Different strategies for meaningful engagement were discussed, with special focus on co-production, where stakeholders actively contribute to the project outputs and their format. The session participants also reflected on potential challenges inherent in communications and stakeholder engagement.

3.4 Storylines session

In addition to the main scientific programme, the Clustering Event featured a guest session by Dave Stainforth (London School of Economics), providing participants with an opportunity to upskill in developing storylines.

What are storylines?

Storylines in climate research are narrative-based representations of plausible futures that help explore how climate-related events might unfold under specific conditions¹. Unlike climate models, storylines focus on causal chains and contextual details, offering a way to understand complex interactions between climate systems, human decisions, and societal impacts. They are beneficial for highlighting uncertainties and examining “what-if” scenarios without quantifying exact probabilities. For example, a storyline might describe how a delayed infrastructure investment in a flood-prone region could interact with a strong El Niño event, increasing disaster risk. By grounding the narratives in climate projections, storylines bridge the gap between scientific models and the real-world concerns of stakeholders, such as decision-makers and policymakers.

During the session, participants practised developing storylines based on plausible scenarios, identifying processes that could lead to dramatic shifts in climate ecosystems (e.g., a dramatic reduction in the AMOC or Amazon deforestation) and processes that could emerge as a result of these changes. This workshop was directly relevant to TipESM, as the development of storylines has been identified as key in the exploitation and communication of project results.

¹ Zappa, G., and T. G. Shepherd (2017). Storylines of Atmospheric Circulation Change for European Regional Climate Impact Assessment. *J. Climate*, **30**, 6561–6577, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0807.1>.

Shepherd, T.G., Boyd, E., Calel, R.A. *et al.* (2018). Storylines: an alternative approach to representing uncertainty in physical aspects of climate change. *Climatic Change*, **151**, 555–571, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-018-2317-9>

Bart J.J.M.. van den Hurk *et al.* (2023). Climate impact storylines for assessing socio-economic responses to remote events, *Climate Risk Management*, **40**, 100500, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2023.100500>

4. Results Achieved and Emerging Recommendations

4.1 Outputs emerging from the Clustering Event

4.1.1 Science Theme 1: Cryosphere

Key outputs and recommendations arising under this theme include:

- Following explanations of the type of simulations being carried out in the TipESM and the ClimTip project, the ClimTip Ice Sheet Models (ISMs) are structured to align with the TIPMIP protocol (i.e. forced by TipESM_core protocol output). TipESM will provide data for additional Global Warming Levels and from more ESMs earlier to the ClimTip modellers.
- The ClimTip ice sheet modelling experts can contribute to the Early Warning Indicator and Risk Register outputs from TipESM. The contributions include sharing examples of suggested templates and information categories to be included.
- Since TipESM and ClimTip have leads active in the TIPMIP Cryosphere domain activity, it was proposed that information can be shared there, given the overlaps between the projects in both ESM and Ice Sheet Modelling work.

4.1.2 Science Theme 2: Biosphere, including Amazon

Key outputs and recommendations arising under this theme include:

- Proposal to use the same Amazon boundary box in TipESM, which ClimTip uses.
- Proposal for TipESM to provide inputs in preparation for an event on Amazon Resilience organized by ClimTip at the 2025 UN Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC COP 30).
- Enhance communication across projects to consolidate experiment configurations.

4.1.3 Science Theme 3: AMOC, SPG, and uncertainties of their projections

Key outputs and recommendations arising under this theme include:

- A follow-up meeting would be beneficial for both projects, and organisers were designated to set up the next meeting.
- Experiment protocols in the two projects were discussed; they are not identical, but are compatible. Synergies were identified, as the two projects focus on different parts of the TIPMIP ocean protocol.

- Links to the newly funded NCAS project PROMOTE, “Progressing Earth System Modelling for Tipping Point Early Warning Systems”, were identified, particularly about the work on early warning indicators related to AMOC and SPG.

4.1.4 Science Theme 4: Tipping points prediction methodology

Key outputs and recommendations arising under this theme include:

- Suggestion for a benchmarking/intercomparison assessment of abrupt shift detection methods, similar to one that was suggested during the ClimTip Annual Meeting’s breakout group discussion.
- Applying slowing down analysis using improved indicators to complex models and ESM data. Emphasis on the need to make indicators efficient enough to be applied to large ensembles.
- The possibility of using spatial stability indicators on ESM output was explored in the context of heterogeneous systems theory, which could help identify key grid cells for analysis.
- Assessing the distribution of critical slowing down (CSD) indicators in piControl to check for uncertainties, biases, and false positives.
- Using uncertainty quantification, including expert uncertainty about parameter values.
- Stability indicators developed in ClimTip and TipESM can be applied in TipESM’s Work Packages 1 and 4.
- Relevant ClimTip project members will join TipESM meetings on data analysis and provide suggestions on methods.
- TipESM can provide ESM data to ClimTip to test the early warning indicators.

4.1.5 Science Theme 5: Impacts and communication of tipping points research results

Key outputs and recommendations arising under this theme include:

- The policy forum run via the OptimESM, TipESM and ClimTip projects was identified as a potential effective way to discuss stakeholder needs with the European Commission.
- The Risk Register - a key output in TipESM - was identified as a starting point to derive storylines and organize our understanding of complex issues in a systematic way.
- A commitment to cross-project collaboration was made, with the aim of covering impact themes more comprehensively, allowing for the provision of quantitative information on more impacts associated with tipping points.

- A cross-project collaboration can also facilitate outreach to more stakeholders across different countries and/or sectors; an example could be a collaboration on participation in international events, such as the UN Climate Change Conference.
- To reach the general public with relevant communications, the projects could collaborate on developing key take-home messages for specific tipping points.

4.2 Actions for further collaboration in the Cluster

- A joint mailing list for Early Career Scientists is to be set up to maintain contact, exchange knowledge, and organize joint events.
- Additional sessions on storylines will be included in the upcoming project meetings, to be held at the beginning of the meetings, allowing discussions and ideas to flourish throughout the meeting duration.

5. Contribution to the TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objectives:

SO9	<p>To provide policy guidance to the EC, IPCC, IPBES and the UNFCC Global Stocktake, on the likelihood and consequences of crossing climate TPs and mitigation options to minimise the chance of such events. KPIs: A summary of the main project findings for non-specialists and leaflets highlighting potential impacts on a) human systems and society b) ecosystems and biodiversity.</p> <p>(Deliverables: D9.2, D9.4, D9.5, D9.7, D10.1 and D10.2)</p>	<p>WP involved: 1-8, 9,10</p>
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	<p>Contribution through this deliverable: The Clustering Event provided a forum for discussing ESM experiment protocols and expected project results, supporting the identification of potential cross-project contributions and synergies, including data, information, and templates. Consequently, it strengthened cross-project collaboration to deliver consolidated and relevant policy guidance based on the results of future projects. Agreed on collaboration related to key policy events: policy fora, briefings, international events (e.g., COP). Increased the knowledge of and commitment to using storylines as a way to organize and communicate our understanding of complex issues systematically.</p>	
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Appendix 1: Agenda of the Clustering Event

Overview of the Clustering Event schedule.

Overview

Time	7/4/2025 (Monday)	8/4/2025 (Tuesday)	9/4/2025 (Wednesday)	10/4/2025 (Thursday)
09:00-10:00		TipESM and ClimTip joint conference	Separate TipESM & ClimTip Annual Meetings	Separate TipESM & ClimTip Annual Meetings
10:00-11:00				
11:00-12:00				
12:00-12:30				
14:00-15:00	TipESM and ClimTip joint conference	TipESM and ClimTip joint conference	Separate TipESM & ClimTip Annual Meetings	TipESM and ClimTip joint event (cross-project breakout groups)
15:00-16:00				
16:00-17:00				
17:00-18:00				

Detailed agenda of the Clustering Event (joint conference and joint event)

Monday 7 April 2025 - TipESM and ClimTip joint conference - AFTERNOON 14:00 - 18:00				
Time	Session	Title/theme	Speaker	Organisation
12:00 - 13:00	Registration & Joint lunch and get together			
13:00 - 13:15	Welcome		Freddy Bouchet	CNRS-IPSL
13:15 - 13:30	Introduction	Introduction to TipESM	Shuting Yang	DMI
13:30 - 13:45	Introduction	Introduction to ClimTip	Niklas Boers / Sebastian Bathiany	TUM
Conference theme 1: Cryosphere				
TipESM session co-lead: Robin Smith (Univ. Reading)				

ClimTip session co-lead: Marisa Montoya (UCM)				
14:00 - 14:28	Keynote talk	The reversibility of ice sheet and sea level responses at different global warming levels in a state-of-the-art Earth System Model	Robin Smith	Univ. Reading
14:28 - 14:35	Q&A / Discussion			
14:35 - 14:50	Short talk	Antarctica's inner values – tapping Antarctica's sub-surface to project its future evolution	Johannes Sutter	Univ. Bern
14:50 - 15:05	Short talk	The fates of the Greenland ice sheet under the idealised scenarios of the TIPMIP-ESM protocol as simulated by EC-Earth3-ESM	Jorge Bernales	DMI
15:05 - 15:20	Short talk	The Antarctic response to a 1% Annual Increase in Atmospheric CO ₂	Javier Blasco	UCM
15:20 - 15:35	Q&A / Discussion			
Conference theme 2: Biosphere incl. Amazon				
TipESM session co-lead: Stefanie Heinicke (PIK Potsdam)				
ClimTip session co-lead: Lucas Ferreira (LMU)				
16:10 - 16:38	Keynote talk	Amazon forest decline driven by both climate change and land-use change	Julia Pongratz	LMU
16:38 - 16:45	Q&A / Discussion			
16:45 - 17:00	Short talk	Bridging Data and Theory for Monitoring Resilience Changes in Tropical Forests	Lana Blaschke	TUM
17:00 - 17:15	Short talk	Disaster-induced displacement as a potential social tipping element	Sandra Zimmermann	PIK
17:15 - 17:30	Short talk	Deep sea and seafloor ecosystem response to net-zero and negative emissions	Friederike Fröb	Univ. Bergen
17:30 -	Q&A / Discussion			

17:45				
Tuesday 8 April 2025 - TipESM and ClimTip joint conference - MORNING 09:00 - 12:15				
Conference theme 3: AMOC, SPG and uncertainties of their projections				
TipESM session co-lead: Juliette Mignot (IPSL)				
ClimTip session co-lead: Richard Wood (Met Office)				
09:05 - 09:33	Keynote talk	On-going and future changes of the AMOC: what can we learn from combining models and various sources of observations?	Didier Swingedouw	Univ. Bordeaux
09:33 - 09:40	Q&A / Discussion			
09:40 - 09:55	Short talk	AMOC thresholds in CMIP6 models: NAHosMIP	Laura Jackson	MetOffice
09:55 - 10:10	Short talk	Reconciled warning signals in observations and models imply approaching AMOC tipping point	Yechul Shin	SNU
10:10 - 10:25	Short talk	Statistically Optimal Fingerprints for the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation and the Sub-Polar Gyre	Bahar Emirzade	TUM
10:25 - 10:40	Q&A / Discussion			
11:15 - 11:30	Short talk	Critical Salinity as an Early Warning of Tipping Point in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre	Lucas Almeida	Univ. Bordeaux
11:30 - 11:45	Short talk	Collapse of the AMOC in a Strongly Eddyng Ocean-Only Model	Henk Dijkstra	Univ. Utrecht
11:45 - 12:00	Short talk	Noise-shaped hysteresis cycles of the AMOC under increasing CO2 forcing	Susanna Corti	CNR-ISAC
12:00 - 12:15	Q&A / Discussion			
Tuesday 8 April 2025 - TipESM and ClimTip joint conference - AFTERNOON 14:00 - 17:15				

Conference theme 4: Tipping points prediction methodology				
TipESM session co-lead: Sybren Drijfhout (KNMI)				
ClimTip session co-lead: Sebastian Bathiany (TUM)				
13:30 - 14:00	Invited talk	Assessment paper on high impact climate events, tipping points and irreversible regional impacts	Gabi Hegerl	Univ. Edinburgh
14:00 - 14:28	Keynote talk	Uncertainties in Tipping Warning and Prediction	Maya Ben-Yami	TUM
14:28 - 14:40	Q&A / Discussion			
14:40 - 14:55	Short talk	Comparing Resilience Concepts in Bifurcating Systems of Intermediate Complexity	Andreas Morr	TUM
14:55 - 15:10	Short talk	Cataloguing abrupt shifts in CMIP6 models: from ocean physics to biogeochemistry	Eike Köhn	IPSL
15:10 - 15:20	Q&A / Discussion			
Conference theme 5: Impacts + Communication of TP results with the public and media				
TipESM session co-lead: Andrew Hartley (Met Office)				
ClimTip session co-lead: Kuat Abeshev (TUM)				
15:55 - 16:23	Invited talk	The IPCC Outlines of AR7 and challenges for WGI	Robert Vautard	IPCC
16:23 - 16:30	Q&A / Discussion			
16:30 - 16:45	Short talk	Tipping Points in Climate Communication: Scientific Consensus, Risk Perception, and Public Engagement	Imke Hoppe	LMU
16:45 - 17:00	Short talk	From Data to Dollars: Making Tipping Points Tangible	Russ Bowdrey	MSCI
17:00 - 17:15	Short talk	Societal and ecosystem impacts of climate tipping points. First results from TipESM	Andrew Hartley	MetO

17:15 - 17:30	Q&A / Discussion
	Networking event with dinner, location: Tour Zamansky

Thu 10 April 2025- TipESM and ClimTip joint event - AFTERNOON 14:30-17:30					
14:00 - 15:05	Cross projects BOG: Cyrosphere	Cross projects BOG: Biosphere	Cross projects BOG: AMOC, SPG	Cross projects BOG: TP prediction methodology	Cross projects BOG: Impacts and communication
15:05 - 15:15	Plenary: ESA projects and linkages to TipESM and ClimTip (Sophie Hebden, ESA)				
15:15 - 15:45	Reporting to the plenary				
16:00 - 17:20	Session on storylines				
17:20 - 17:30	Wrap up and way forward.				